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Fabrication and Characterization of a Plasmonic Ellipsoidal Nanohole Array With Chiral Response

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a novel approach to fabricate plasmonic nanohole arrays with intrinsic chiral behavior using displacement Talbot lithography, demonstrating a significant dichroic signal of 20%–30% and highlighting its potential for the scalable fabrication of chiral plasmonic platforms. We experimentally confirm that a strong chiroptical effect is achieved by introducing ellipsoidal nanoholes with their principal axes rotated by 18° relative to the principal axes of a square array, a strong circular dichroism response is achieved, which contrasts with the achiral response of circular nanohole arrays. Both experimental and numerical results confirm that the rotation of the ellipsoidal nanohole principal axes with respect to array symmetry lines breaks mirror symmetry, thus enabling circular dichroism even at normal incidence. This approach offers promising applications in chiral sensing and biomolecule optical detection.

1 | Introduction

Interest in the chiral properties of materials has existed since the discovery of circular dichroism (CD) in the 19th century [1]. This optical feature has been extensively studied, particularly in organic and biological molecules [2], where chirality can fundamentally impact their behavior and interaction with the surrounding environment. Such interaction is crucial for the development of biomolecules essential to modern pharmaceutical technology [3, 4]. Consequently, there is an urgent need to develop sophisticated techniques for the precise detection of dichroism in small samples. While improvements have been made to existing methods [5], significant effort has also been devoted to studying nanostructured photonic and plasmonic platforms, driven by advances in sensing devices based on these technologies [6].

Studies on these platforms typically aim for two outcomes: first, to leverage electromagnetic radiation–matter interaction to enhance the chiral signal of molecules; and second, to engineer metastructures for the creation of artificial materials with controlled chirality [7, 8].

Among the proposed structures, particular attention has focused on metallic nanoparticles, both for signal enhancement [9, 10] and for chirality engineering [11, 12].

Additionally, planar ordered arrays of nanoholes, often called nanohole arrays (NHAs), are worth mentioning. Since their features are designed for a specific function (chirality, in this case), they are sometimes referred to as metasurfaces or metamaterials [13–15].

Both dielectric- and metallic-based metamaterials have been investigated to improve interaction with chiral molecules [16–23], though the primary focus is generally on generating and manipulating chiral effects [24, 25].

For NHAs, the simplest arrangement is a square array of circular nanoholes [26]. A common variant uses ellipsoidal nanoholes [25, 27]. As shown in the literature, circular nanoholes are intrinsically achiral, as are ellipsoidal nanoholes when their principal axes are aligned with the symmetry lines of the array [26].

It has been established that, in addition to the intrinsic chirality, an extrinsic one can be observed even in achiral samples. This is

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FIGURE 1 | Schematics of the fabrication process.

a result of the mutual orientation between the sample's structure and the incident electromagnetic wave [14, 27]. A large dichroic signal can thus be obtained by changing the angle of incidence away from the surface normal and/or by rotating the plane of incidence relative to the surface symmetry lines.

However, a comparable dichroic signal can be measured even at normal incidence when the principal axes of the ellipsoidal nanoholes are rotated and misaligned with respect to the symmetry lines of the array [22].

Several theoretical papers have considered this specific case, describing simulated chiral responses based on field distributions and investigating the optimization of structural parameters for chirality enhancement [21, 22, 25, 27, 28].

Despite these theoretical/computational studies, only a few papers report measurements on real samples [29–31], and these studies are often only partial, focusing on polarization-dependent responses with no mention of dichroic behavior.

The present study aims to address this lack of information by focusing on two complementary issues. First, we describe a new approach to fabricate plasmonic NHAs with rotated ellipsoidal nanoholes, which exhibit intrinsic chiral behavior. We achieve this using displacement Talbot lithography (DTL), a promising nanofabrication method capable of producing high-resolution periodic patterns over large areas, making it suitable for scalable sensing applications. Second, we experimentally measured the dichroic signal of these samples, also reinforced by the evaluation of the Stokes' parameters, to confirm the theoretical predictions. Besides, to support both points, we performed a series of Finite-Difference Time-Domain (FDTD) simulations.

2 | Experimental Details

2.1 | Growing Technique

DTL is a relatively new technology for high-resolution photolithography technique that combines the benefits of compact, mask-based Talbot lithography with the high depth of focus of interference lithography, enabling robust nanopatterning on a wafer scale. The principle of DTL is illustrated in Figure 1. In conventional Talbot lithography, a wafer with a UV-sensitive photoresist is placed at a specific Talbot plane to transfer the Talbot image into a pattern. This process requires extremely tight tolerance on the distance between the mask and the photoresist, which in turn necessitates expensive, high-quality, and very flat wafers with low Bow/WARP characteristics. Consequently, achieving reliable Talbot lithography on large wafers is very challenging. This challenge was addressed by Solak et al. [32] who demonstrated that by continuously changing the

distance between the mask and the wafer during exposure, the pattern becomes independent of the specific mask-to-wafer distance. This is because the process averages the intensity along the Talbot pattern propagation, ensuring a uniform dose in the nanoholes.

In our case, we aimed at patterning the nanoholes array with a pitch $p=450$ nm. This requires a mask with a periodic square nanohole array. The aerial image of such a mask corresponds to a square hole array rotated by 45° , with a pitch reduced by a factor of $\sqrt{2}$. Therefore, we used a mask with a $p=635$ nm to achieve the target 450 nm pitch.

The fabrication process is described below.

Substrates were 100 mm diameter, 500 μm thick round Schott glass wafers. A 5 nm layer of Cr (as an adhesion layer) and a 100 nm layer of Au were deposited onto the wafers by electron beam evaporation (Evatek BAK Uni). The wafers were then coated with an AZ BARLI-II antireflective layer and a PFI-88A7 photoresist layer from SUMIRESIST (Figure 1, Step 1). The DTL exposures were performed using a PhableR 200C tool (Eulitha AG) with 377 nm wavelength and unpolarized light. The Talbot distance, calculated using the equation $d=2P^2/\lambda$, was ≈ 2.14 μm . During the 60-second exposure, the sample was scanned over 10 Talbot distances (21.4 μm) to ensure a uniform dose in the nanoholes [33]. To create the desired elongated nanoholes, the sample was also scanned laterally at an angle of 18° relative to the array's x -axis. After exposure, the PFI was developed in MF24A (Figure 1, Step 2), and the BARLI-II layer was etched using reactive ion etching in an oxygen plasma (Figure 1, Step 3). The Au layer was then etched by Ar ion milling in an Oxford IonFab300 tool at a 10° angle on a rotating chuck (20 rpm), with a beam current of 55 mA and a beam voltage of 300 V for 12 min (Figure 1, Step 4). The remaining organic layers (BARLI/PFI) were removed by oxygen plasma (Figure 1, Step 5). A final annealing treatment using an oven was performed keeping the sample for 1 h in air at 300°C to make uniform and compact the gold layer and smooth some residual irregularities induced by Ar ion milling in the proximity of nanoholes apertures.

2.2 | Optical Characterization

To investigate the intrinsic chiral response of the ellipsoidal NHA, reflectance (R), and transmittance (T) were measured at normal incidence using a Bruker IFS66s Fourier transform interferometer coupled to a custom-built reflectometer as depicted in the scheme shown in Figure 2.

Both linearly and circularly polarized light were used for these measurements. The beam was centered on the sample, with the sample's surface normal aligned along the optical axis of the setup. This configuration allowed us to vary the alignment of the ellipsoidal nanoholes

FIGURE 2 | Optical measurement scheme.

relative to different source polarization states by adjusting the sample's azimuthal angle. For the sake of completeness, the collected R and T spectra for the different source polarization configurations and the set-up details are provided in the supporting information.

Diffuse light measurements were performed with an Agilent Cary 6000i spectrophotometer at normal incidence resorting to its built-in Ulbricht integrating sphere tool.

2.3 | Numerical Simulations

A custom particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithm, implemented in Ansys Lumerical FDTD (release 2024 R2.3, v8.32.3941), was used to design the NHA, as previously reported by Angelini et al. [34, 35]. This design routine incorporated the practical constraints of our fabrication method. FDTD numerical simulations were performed to optimize the NHA geometry to finely tune the dichroic response, with the goal of centering its maximum approximately in the (500 ÷ 1000)nm spectral region of interest.

A reference structure with a gold film thickness of 80 nm, a pitch of 450 nm, and a hole diameter of 190 nm was identified. We fabricated two NHA structures using the DTL method described in Section 2.1: one with circular nanoholes to serve as a non-dichroic reference, and a second with an ellipsoidal shape to exhibit dichroic behavior.

Consequently, the specific geometrical parameters of the fabricated ellipsoidal NHA were determined from SEM images and imported into Ansys Lumerical FDTD to create an accurate computational model of the actual samples. This model was designed to mimic the optical behavior of the main plasmonic modes. The ellipsoidal nanoholes were modeled by combining two overlapping ellipses, slightly shifted along their major axis, to mimic the experimental fabrication process, specifically the oscillation of the lithography mask. This model is geometrically defined by five parameters: (i) pitch, (ii) minor axis length, (iii) major axis length, (iv) shift along the major axis, and (v) major axis rotation angle with respect to the square array x direction. The optimized values used in the simulations were: $p=450$ nm, Minor axis=130 nm, Major axis=190 nm, Shift=10 nm, and Rotation angle=18°.

FIGURE 3 | SEM images of the fabricated square arrays with pitch 450 nm. Circular and ellipsoidal nanoholes are shown respectively on the left and right panels. The major axes of the ellipsoidal nanoholes are rotated by 18° relative to the array x direction.

For each set of parameters, air-filled ellipsoidal nanoholes are embedded within an 80 nm thick Au film, and both are placed on a semi-infinite SiO₂ substrate, consistently with the design routine. The FDTD technical details are reported in Supporting Information.

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Surface Analysis

The SEM images of the fabricated structures with circular and elongated nanoholes are shown in Figure 3. From a geometric analysis of these images, we determined that the pitch for both arrays is 450 nm. The diameter of the circular nanoholes is ≈235 nm. For the elongated nanoholes, the shape can be approximated as an ellipse with a minor axis of nearly 165 nm and a major axis of 245 nm. Crucially, these ellipsoidal nanoholes are rotated by 18° with respect to the array's symmetry direction.

3.2 | Optical Analysis

According to literature, CD was defined as

$$CD = \frac{A_{\text{left}} - A_{\text{right}}}{A_{\text{left}} + A_{\text{right}}} \quad (1)$$

where A_{left} and A_{right} indicate the absorbance for left- and right-handed circularly polarized light, respectively.

Thanks to the quality of the array, the low divergence of the beam and the absence of diffracted beams in the spectral region under investigation, A signals were evaluated as

$$A_{\text{left, right}} = 1 - R_{\text{left, right}} - T_{\text{left, right}} \quad (2)$$

The A_{left} and A_{right} are presented in Figure 4a,b for circular and ellipsoidal nanoholes, respectively. The evaluated A signals do not consider any influences due to scattered light, not accounted for in Equation (2). As reported in the supporting information, in the spectral region under investigation, from 500 to 1000 nm, a diffuse component is present with values of a few percent, roughly proportional to the total reflectance. Such an effect does not significantly impact the behavior of the DC signals while it influences its absolute value. It is worth highlighting that the subtraction of a background due to diffused light tends to increase the CD values, thus our CD is underestimated.

The CD resulting signals are shown in Figure 4c.

For the ellipsoidal nanoholes, a dichroic effect as large as 20%–30% is observed, with signal changes corresponding to different absorption structures. To confirm that this effect is related to the shape and orientation of the nanoholes, we performed the same measurements on the sample with circular nanoholes, see Figure 3, which serves as

FIGURE 4 | Experimental A signal collected under circularly polarized light (CPL) of opposite handedness for (a) circular and (b) ellipsoidal nanoholes. The corresponding measured CD signal is reported in (c).

an achiral reference. As shown in Figure 4a, no significant difference is noticeable between the A spectra for left- and right-polarized light in this sample. The small DC residual dichroic signal observed in Figure 4c for the circular nanohole array could be attributed to sample imperfections, inhomogeneity, minor alignment tolerances in the experimental setup regarding all the optical components, with particular regard to sample, polarizers, and quarter wave plate, or its phase shift due to manufacturing flaws, especially in low-absorption regions. To summarize, such a small DC signal effectively defines a practical confidence limit for our dichroic effect intensity evaluation.

Measurements with linearly polarized light revealed, instead, a significant dependence on the alignment of the polarization axis with respect to the principal axes of the ellipsoidal nanoholes. Figure 5 shows the experimental A spectra for linearly polarized light aligned along the long and short axes of the ellipsoidal nanoholes.

The spectrum corresponding to the short-axis alignment exhibits two main broad absorption features: one in the infrared region at 800 nm (with a shoulder around 850 nm) and a second with a maximum at ≈ 640 nm. These two structures are separated by a low-absorption region between 670 and 750 nm. Similarly, the long-axis alignment spectrum also shows two main structures: a narrow one at 730 nm and a broader one with a maximum around 580 nm.

It is noteworthy that the A spectra measured with circularly polarized light consistently shows all the absorption features observed with linear polarization, specifically at 580, 640, 730, and 800 nm. This effect, also evident in the R and T spectra (see Figure S11) arises from the superposition of the two resonances corresponding to the EF oscillating along the principal axes of the ellipsoidal scatterers. The key difference between right- and left-handed circularly polarized light is the relative weight of the intensities of these absorption features.

A common low-absorption point is observed at 700 nm, which corresponds to the folding point in the dispersion pattern of the surface plasmon polaritons (SPPs) at the gold-glass interface, indicating a likely band gap opening.

3.3 | FDTD Simulation Results

The computational A and CD curves were calculated using FDTD simulations. The results show excellent agreement with both

FIGURE 5 | Measured A signals for ellipsoidal nanoholes with linearly polarized light along the short- and long-axis of the ellipsoidal hole.

the SEM images and the optical characterization outcomes, as illustrated in Figure 6.

We first considered the A responses for linearly polarized light aligned along the ellipsoidal axes. This step was crucial for validating the computational model against the real NHA. As shown in Figure 6a, the simulations successfully reproduce all the resonances observed experimentally in Figure 5, including the peak positions and intensities. This confirms that the ellipsoidal nanohole shape properly breaks the symmetry and can support a dichroic response.

Next, we replicated the measurements from Figure 4b for left- and right-handed circularly polarized light. Figure 6b shows that the FDTD simulations effectively mimic the experimental response. The two simulated A curves satisfactorily reproduce their experimental counterparts, both individually and in their mutual comparison, particularly regarding peak positions and relative intensity variations.

Finally, the simulated dichroic signal for the ellipsoidal nanoholes was calculated using the same definition as Equation (1). The resulting curve, shown in Figure 6c, demonstrates a good agreement with the experimental data in Figure 4c, both in terms of signal behavior, peak positions, and intensities. This strong correspondence across all simulated signals with their measured counterparts corroborates the reliability of our computational NHA model, confirming that the geometrical, morphological, and optical features can be accurately modeled and controlled. This

provides high confidence in our understanding and ability to manipulate the behavior of the main plasmonic modes.

3.4 | Discussion

The high quality and large-area uniformity of the NHAs, enabled by the precise control of the DTL fabrication parameters, allow both experimental and numerical results to confirm that a square array of ellipsoidal nanoholes with rotated axis with respect to the array directions, induces a strong circular dichroic response. This is in stark contrast to a square array of circular nanoholes, which remain optically achiral as reported in Figure 4a.

As shown in Figure 4b and confirmed by the simulations in Figure 6b, the two sets of resonances behave differently when excited by left- or right-handed circularly polarized light. The lack of mirror symmetry, introduced by the 18° rotation of the ellipsoidal axes relative to the lattice directions, imparts intrinsic chiral properties to the surface, resulting in a marked dichroic response at normal incidence.

This phenomenon has been investigated theoretically by Ali et al. [22], but our work represents the first experimental confirmation of this effect, demonstrating that its behavior aligns with theoretical predictions. According to Ali et al. [22], CPL excites both sets of resonant modes, but because these are propagating SPP modes, the lack of mirror symmetry introduces a phase delay that depends on the handedness of the CPL. This has been shown by studying the field dynamics of these modes, demonstrating that circular dichroism arises from the unbalanced interference between field components polarized along the long- and short-axes of the elliptical nanoholes. When these components combine with a $\pm 90^\circ$ phase delay (representing left- and right-circularly polarized light), the broken symmetry of the tilted nanoholes creates a magnitude difference, resulting in the measured CD signal.

Indeed, as depicted in Figure 5, and consistent with data from Angelini et al. [31], two sets of plasmonic resonances mutually orthogonal are observed in the spectra, concerning the orientation of the electric field along the two axes of the ellipsoidal section of the holes. The array's periodicity also plays a significant role in defining the spectral curves, as evidenced by the plasmonic band gap opening at 700 nm, directly related to the pitch.

Starting from this finding, we investigated the array's ability to modify the polarization state of the incident radiation, also known as optical activity (OA). We conducted a series of measurements using linearly polarized light to evaluate the phase delay by collecting the Stokes parameters referred to the transmitted beam [36].

Consistent with Figure 5, we considered two cases with the polarization axis aligned along the main axes of the ellipsoidal nanoholes. A detailed description of the measurement procedure is provided in the supporting information.

The measured Stokes parameters for linearly polarized light aligned along the short and long axes are reported in Figure 7a,e, respectively. The Stokes parameters allow us to analyze the polarization features of the transmitted light and the state of the polarization ellipse (PE) for its polarized fraction [37], which can be geometrically represented as a point on the Poincaré sphere. Ultimately, by analyzing the Stokes parameters, it is possible to investigate the relationship between OA and polarization singularity [38].

FIGURE 6 | Simulated A signals for ellipsoidal nanoholes in the case of (a) linearly and (b) circularly polarized light. (c) Simulated dichroic signal calculated from A signals in (b).

FIGURE 7 | Measured Stokes parameters for linearly polarized light aligned along the (a) short-axis, indicated with subscript *s*, and (e) long-axis, indicated with subscript *l*, of the ellipsoidal hole. Elliptical polarization degree, polarization degree, and rotation angle are reported in panels (b) and (f), (c) and (g), (d) and (h) for incoming linearly polarized light aligned along the short- and long-axis of the ellipsoidal hole, respectively.

The first parameter derived analyzing the Stokes parameters is the degree of elliptical polarization identified through the angle

$$\chi = \frac{1}{2} \text{tg}^{-1} \left(\frac{S_3}{\sqrt{S_1^2 + S_2^2}} \right) \quad (3)$$

and operatively defined through the evolution of $\text{tg}(\chi)$ as reported in Figure 8 for linearly polarized light aligned along the short-, panel (b), and long-axis, panel (f), of the ellipsoidal hole, respectively. In this way, $\text{tg}(\chi) = \pm 1$ identifies a state of circular polarization (i.e., the semi-axes of the ellipse are equal) and consequently an S_3 value close to ± 1 is expected.

For the sake of completeness, χ is plotted in Figure S14c.

The second parameter derived analyzing the Stokes parameters is the polarization degree

$$\text{PD} = \frac{\sqrt{S_1^2 + S_2^2 + S_3^2}}{S_0} \quad (4)$$

indicating the fraction of the polarized light on the total, plotted for linearly polarized light aligned along the short- (Figure 7c), and long-axis (Figure 7g), of the ellipsoidal hole.

Finally, the third parameter derived analyzing the Stokes parameters is the angle

$$\Psi = \frac{1}{2} \text{tg}^{-1} \left(\frac{S_2}{S_1} \right) \quad (5)$$

FIGURE 8 | Comparison between the CD signals evaluated from A signals as in Equation (1) and as a linear combination of the S_3 parameters normalized to the total intensity as in Equation (8).

describing the rotation of the PE long-axis in the xy -plane with respect to the x -axis.

The values of Ψ are plotted in Figure 7: panel (d) refers to an incoming linearly polarized light aligned along the short-axis of the ellipsoidal hole while panel (h) refers to linearly polarized light aligned along the long-axis of the ellipsoidal hole.

The two distinct linearly polarized modes observed in Figure 5 are expected to preserve their polarization state, but this holds true

only partially, specifically in the spectral regions corresponding to the main optical resonance for each configuration (around 800 nm for short-axis polarization and 730 nm for long-axis polarization).

As shown in Figure 7d,h, the main polarization axis is rotated by -23° and 67° , respectively, at the corresponding wavelength. However, a relatively strong perpendicular component is also present (as indicated by a non-zero $\tan(\chi)$ value), and the polarization state becomes even more complex in other spectral regions.

The wavelength dependence of S1 and S2, reflected in the evolution of \mathcal{P} , shows that the linear components of the polarization direction are changing. The evolution of S3 shows that $\tan(\chi)$ tends to increase toward ± 1 (circular polarization) around 730 nm for light polarized along the short-axis and 800 nm for light polarized along the long-axis. It is important to note that these wavelengths correspond to the resonances of the perpendicular polarization direction, as shown in Figure 5.

The peaks in the $\tan(\chi)$ plots do not directly correspond to those in the S3 spectra because $\tan(\chi)$ is a normalized quantity, describing only the features of the polarized component of the transmitted light.

To enable a direct comparison, the Stokes parameters were normalized to the radius of the Poincaré sphere

$$S_{i_{\text{norm}}} = \frac{S_i}{R} \text{ with } i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (6)$$

where

$$R = \sqrt{S_1^2 + S_2^2 + S_3^2} \quad (7)$$

and according to these new parameters the weight of S1, S2, and S3 on the polarization state can be appreciated. These three parameters describe only the polarization state of the polarized component, and any information relating to the non-polarized part is lost.

The normalized Stokes parameters, plotted in Figure SI4 of the Supporting Information, clearly show the correspondence between the peaks in the $S_{3_{\text{norm}}}$ curve and the $\tan(\chi)$ plot. This outcome aligns with the model proposed by Schäferling et al. [39], which suggests that the polarization of the incident radiation does not dictate the transmitted polarization but rather determines the excitation efficiency of the NHA's eigenmodes, thus defining the chiral response. Through this effect, the plasmonic NHA can modify the polarization of the incident beam into a new state that depends on the morphological, symmetry, and geometrical properties of the scatterer.

Furthermore, since S3 is related to CD, the change in sign for the two cases (short- and long-axis alignment) suggests that each configuration corresponds to a series of eigenmodes with different chirality. Since the total dichroic signal exhibits both positive and negative components in different spectral regions, it can be interpreted as a combination of these eigenmodes.

When a linear combination of the S3 parameters is normalized to the total intensity as

$$CD(S_3) = \frac{S_{3_l} + S_{3_s}}{S_{0_l} + S_{0_s}} \quad (8)$$

a curve very similar to the one plotted in Figure 4 panel (c), evaluated from Equation (1), is produced as depicted in Figure 8. The subscripts s and l stand for short- and long-axis alignment and refer to the curves plotted in Figure 7 panels (a) and (e) showing the measured Stokes parameters for linearly polarized light aligned along the short- and long-axis of the ellipsoidal hole, respectively. The excellent agreement, both in spectral features and quantitative values, provides strong evidence for the direct relationship between the measured Stokes parameters and the observed CD signals.

4 | Conclusion

In this work, we have successfully demonstrated the scalable fabrication of intrinsically chiral NHAs using DTL. By geometrically engineering ellipsoidal nanoholes rotated at 18° , we achieved a strong CD response. Both experimental measurements and numerical simulations confirmed that breaking the mirror symmetry of the NHA via rotated ellipsoidal nanoholes induces a pronounced CD signal of 20%–30% at normal incidence, an effect completely absent in achiral, circular NHAs.

Our FDTD simulations validated the experimental optical behavior and provided crucial insight, revealing that the dichroic effect arises from phase delays between excited SPP modes under circularly polarized light of opposite handedness. Furthermore, a comprehensive Stokes parameter analysis elucidated the NHA's ability to manipulate the polarization state of light, thereby linking chiral near-field interactions to far-field optical activity.

This study successfully bridges theoretical predictions with experimental realization, offering a robust and practical platform for chiral plasmonics. The DTL-based approach enables large-area, high-throughput fabrication, a critical requirement for real-world applications such as chiral sensing, biomolecule detection, and polarization-sensitive photonic devices.

Future studies could explore the dynamic coupling of chirality with external stimuli or integration with dielectric metasurfaces for enhanced functionality.

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Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Supporting Fig. S1:** Reflectance and transmittance for ellipsoidal holes measured with circularly (a) and linearly (b) polarized light. **Supporting Fig. S2:** Total reflected (red curve) and diffuse (black curve) light intensities collected using an integrating sphere. **Supporting Fig. S3:** Optical measurement scheme used to evaluate the Stokes parameters through the collection of the transmitted signal. **Supporting Fig. S4:** Normalized Stokes parameters, for linearly polarized light aligned along the short- (a) and long-axis (b) of the ellipsoidal hole, respectively. The degree of elliptical polarization is reported in panel (c).